
AI-ENHANCED ECG ALGORITHMS FOR ATRIAL FIBRILLATION DIAGNOSIS

Gurram Saathwika ¹, Ojukwu Esther ², Dr. Keerthi Palagati ³

1. Dr. Pinnamaneni Siddhartha Institute of medical science and research foundation, Chinna Avutapalli, Andhra Pradesh, India
2. Kyiv Medical University (Polish Campus), Bytom City, Poland
3. Department of Medicine and surgery, Govt medical college Anantapur, India.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13828639

Introduction: Atrial fibrillation (AF), a common and serious cardiac arrhythmia, can lead to stroke and heart failure if not diagnosed early. Traditional ECG interpretation is effective but limited by human error and specialist expertise. Recent advances in AI-enhanced ECG algorithms may improve AF diagnosis accuracy, speed, and accessibility. These algorithms use machine learning to analyze large datasets and detect subtle AF patterns and anomalies more accurately than conventional methods.

Review: Recent research demonstrates significant advances in AI-enhanced ECG algorithms for atrial fibrillation diagnosis and management. AI-augmented ECGs can detect AF signatures even in normal sinus rhythm, making them useful for early and accurate AF diagnosis [1]. This allows for timely intervention, reducing stroke and other AF associated complications. AI-integrated wearable devices can monitor continuous AF with high sensitivity and specificity, making them suitable for long-term cardiac monitoring [2]. AF-risk individuals benefit from real-time health tracking with these advances. AI's ECG-based prediction of future AF episodes complements traditional risk scores like CHARGE-AF, improving prognostic accuracy and helping healthcare providers manage and mitigate risks [2]. Since deep learning and machine learning can analyse complex data patterns and extract meaningful insights from ECG data, these AI-driven methods are increasingly being used in clinical practice to improve AF detection and prediction [3].

Despite these promising advances, AI retains certain limitations: Lack of diversity in training datasets can introduce bias into AI algorithms, leading to inequities in care. Wearable devices using single-channel ECGs and photoplethysmography (PPG) sensors may miss subtle signs of AF or other conditions [4, 5]. Wearable devices' long-term reliability and durability in different environments and patient populations need further study [5]. AI tool integration into clinical workflows can be complicated, requiring healthcare providers to change their practice and education. More diverse and representative datasets improved wearable devices, and AI integration into clinical decision-making should be the focus of future research. Using AI-enhanced ECGs for more cardiac and non-cardiac conditions beyond AF detection could improve patient care and make it more comprehensive and personalized.

Conclusion: AI-enhanced ECG algorithms represent a significant advancement in the diagnosis and management of atrial fibrillation (AF). These technologies improve early detection, continuous monitoring, and predictive capabilities, offering substantial benefits for patient care. However, addressing current limitations, such as data diversity, device reliability, and clinical integration, and exploring new research avenues are critical to maximizing their potential and ensuring their successful integration into clinical practice. Ensuring equitable healthcare outcomes remains essential as these technologies evolve.

Keywords: Atrial fibrillation (AF), Electrocardiogram (ECG), Artificial Intelligence, AF-Diagnostic algorithm

References:

1. Baek, S., Kwon, S., You, S. C., Lee, N., Yu, H. T., Lee, R., Roh, Y., Kim, H., Shin, S. Y., Lee, D. I., Park, J., Park, Y. M., Suh, Y. J., Choi, K., Lee, C., Joung, B., Choi, W., & Kim, H. (2023). Artificial intelligence-enhanced 12-lead electrocardiography for identifying atrial fibrillation during sinus rhythm (AIAFib) trial: Protocol for a multicenter retrospective study. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2023.1258167>.
2. Harmon, D. M., Sehrawat, O., Maanja, M., Wight, J., & Noseworthy, P. A. (2023). Artificial Intelligence for the Detection and Treatment of Atrial Fibrillation. *Arrhythmia & Electrophysiology Review*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.15420/aer.2022.31>.
3. Zhang, Y., Xu, S., Xing, W., Chen, Q., Liu, X., Pu, Y., Xin, F., Jiang, H., Yin, Z., Tao, D., Zhou, D., Zhu, Y., Yuan, B., Jin, Y., He, Y., Wu, Y., Po, S. S., Wang, H., & Benditt, D. G. (2024). Robust Artificial Intelligence Tool for Atrial Fibrillation Diagnosis: Novel Development Approach Incorporating Both Atrial Electrograms and Surface ECG and Evaluation by Head-to-Head Comparison With Hospital-Based Physician ECG Readers. *Journal of the American Heart Association: Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Disease*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.1161/JAHA.123.032100>.
4. Suzuki, S., Motogi, J., Nakai, H., Matsuzawa, W., Takayanagi, T., Umemoto, T., Hirota, N., Hyodo, A., Satoh, K., Otsuka, T., Arita, T., Yagi, N., & Yamashita, T. (2022). Identifying patients with atrial fibrillation during sinus rhythm on ECG: Significance of the labeling in the artificial intelligence algorithm. *International Journal of Cardiology. Heart & Vasculature*, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcha.2022.100954>.
5. Mohamoud A, Jensen J, Buda KG. Consumer-grade wearable cardiac monitors: What they do well, and what needs work. *Cleve Clin J Med*. 2024;91(1):23-29. Published 2024 Jan 2. [doi:10.3949/ccjm.91a.23030](https://doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.91a.23030).